

Supplemental Table 1: Grids used in the hyperparameter tuning stage for each machine learning (ML) model.

ML Algorithm	Grid
Deep	hidden (number of layers and neurons per layer)= [(5, 5, 5, 5, 5), (10, 10, 10, 10), (50, 50, 50), (100, 100, 100)]; epochs (number of times to iterate (stream) the dataset)= [5, 10, 50, 100, 200]; L1 regularization= [0, 1×10^{-5} , 1×10^{-4}]; rate (learning rate)= [0, 0.01, 0.005, 0.001]; rho (adaptive learning rate time decay factor)= [0, 0.01, 0.005, 0.001]; input dropout ratio= [0, 0.1, 0.2]
RF	ntrees (number of trees)= [5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, 60, 65, 70, 75, 80, 85, 90, 95, 100]; mtries (number of columns to randomly select at each level)= [5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, 60, 65, 70, 75, 80, 85, 90, 95, 100]; sample rate (row sample rate per tree)= [0.5, 0.8, 1]
xgboost	eta (learning rate) = [0.001, 0.01, 0.05]; max_depth (learning rate) = [5,10]; min_child_weight (minimum sum of instance weight (hessian) needed in a child) = [1,5,10]; subsample (subsample ratio of the training instance) = 1; colsample_bytree (subsample ratio of columns when constructing each tree) = [0.5, 0.8, 1]
SVM	C (regularization parameter that controls the trade-off between achieving a low training error and minimizing the margin violation) = [0, 0.105, 0.211, 0.316, 0.421, 0.526, 0.632, 0.737, 0.842, 0.947, 1.053, 1.158, 1.263, 1.368, 1.474, 1.579, 1.684, 1.789, 1.895, 2]

Deep: multi-layer feedforward artificial neural network; RF: Random Forest; xgboost: extreme gradient boosting; SVM: Support Vector Machine.